

Infrared Spectra of Chalkones Derived from Hydroxychloro-acetophenones

A. Nayak, P. L. Nayak, B. K. Sabata, and M. K. Rout

IR spectra of some chalkones derived from 3-chloro-2-hydroxy-, 3-chloro-4-hydroxy-, and 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-acetophenones have been studied and some interesting generalisations on structure-spectra correlation with regard to carbonyl and ethylenic absorption have been made.

In the present communication IR spectra of some chalkones derived from 3-chloro-2-hydroxy-, 3-chloro-4-hydroxy-, and 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-acetophenones have been studied. These acetophenones were obtained by the Fries migration of *o*-chloro- and *p*-chloro-phenylacetates by using methods similar to those followed by Shah and Parikh¹.

The chalkones No. 1 to No. 23 (Table I) were prepared by using 50% sodium hydroxide as the condensing agent². The chalkones No. 1, 2, 4, 8, 9, and 11 were prepared by using 10% sodium methoxide as the condensing agent³. The chalkones No. 24-29 were prepared by effecting the condensation in presence of boric acid (*M/5*), potassium chloride (*M/5*), and sodium hydroxide (*M/5*) (buffer of pH 7.8)⁴.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	Yield.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1.	2'-Hydroxy 3'-chloro-C	120°	95%	13.41	13.73
2.	2'-Hydroxy 3'-chloro-4-methoxy-C	145°	90	12.20	12.30
3.	2,2'-Dihydroxy-3'-chloro-C	180-81°	50	12.87	12.93
4.	2'-Hydroxy-3',2-dichloro-C	152°	90	23.68	23.97
5.	1-(3'-Chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(furfuryl)-P	116°	60	14.17	14.28
6.	1-(3'-Chloro-2'-hydroxy)-3-(1-naphthyl)-P	161°	80	11.39	11.50
7.	1-(3'-Chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(styryl)-P	125°	95	12.32	12.46
8.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-C	114°	82	13.29	13.74
9.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-4-methoxy-C	113°	85	12.28	12.35
10.	2,2'-Dihydroxy-5'-chloro-C	160°	70	12.78	12.93
11.	2'-Hydroxy-5',2-dichloro-C	155°	80	23.53	23.68
12.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-4-isopropyl-C	95°	60	11.76	11.81
13.	1-(5'-Chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(1-furfuryl)-P	90°	55	14.19	14.28
14.	1-(5'-Chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(1-naphthyl)-P	164°	80	11.42	11.50
15.	1-(5'-Chloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(styryl)-P	135°	95	12.49	12.57
16.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-C	160°	53	13.68	13.74
17.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-methoxy-C	107°	60	12.19	12.34

1. *This Journal*, 1959, 36, 784.

2. Mahal and Venkatraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 617.

3. Bohrmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1856.

4. Reichel and Hempel, *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 3395.

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	Yield.	%Chlorine.	
				Found.	Reqd.
18.	4'-Hydroxy-3',2-dichloro-C	185°	65%	23.48	23.68
19.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-nitro-C	176°	25	11.56	11.67
20.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-3-nitro-C	230°	30	11.60	11.69
21.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-nitro-C	248°	25	11.61	11.67
22.	1-(3'-Chloro-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(furfuryl)-P	140°	45	14.13	14.28
23.	1-(3'-Chloro-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(1-naphthyl)-P	202°	70	11.46	11.50
24.	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-nitro-C	200°(d)	45	11.52	11.69
25.	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-3-nitro-C	160°	60	11.60	11.69
26.	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-nitro-C	175°	70	11.58	11.69
27.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-2-nitro-C	200°	90	11.48	11.69
28.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-3-nitro-C	220°	90	11.58	11.69
29.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-4-nitro-C	205°	90	11.53	11.69
30.	2'-Acetoxy-3'-chloro-C	94°	50	11.50	11.51
31.	4'-Acetoxy-3'-chloro-C	110°	70	11.46	11.91
32.	2'-Acetoxy-3',2-dichloro-C	157°	60	20.93	21.19
33.	2'-Acetoxy-5',2-dichloro-C	65°	70	20.73	21.19
34.	2'-Acetoxy-5'-chloro-C	108°	75	11.29	11.81
35.	2'-Acetoxy-3'-chloro-4-methoxy-C	123°	75	10.29	10.59
36.	2'-Acetoxy-5'-chloro-4-methoxy-C	85°	70	10.21	10.59
37.	2'-Methoxy-3'-chloro-C	136°	65	12.98	13.02
38.	2'-Methoxy-5'-chloro-C	71°	70	12.89	13.02
39.	4'-Methoxy-3'-chloro-C	134°	65	13.55	13.02
40.	2'-Methoxy-3,2-dichloro-C	131°	60	23.09	23.13
41.	2'-Methoxy-5',2-dichloro-C	80°	70	23.08	23.13
42.	2',4-Dimethoxy-3'-chloro-C	122°	60	11.60	11.73
43.	2',4-Dimethoxy-5'-chloro-C	91°	70	11.69	11.73

N.B. C stands for chalcone and P, for propenone.

The chalcones No. 1, 3, 8, 10, 16, and 17 (Table I) have already been reported by Shah and Parikh⁵, but in the present work, these have been prepared by methods different from those followed by the previous workers.

Some of the hydroxychalcones have been acetylated (by using acetic anhydride and pyridine) and methylated (by using dimethyl sulphate in acetone in presence of K_2CO_3).

EXPERIMENTAL

2'-Hydroxy-3'-chlorochalcone: Method I.—To a solution of 3-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.17 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.11 ml) in minimum quantity of hot aldehyde-free ethanol was added 50% NaOH solution (0.68 ml). The mixture was kept at the room temperature for 12 hr. The solid separating was decomposed by ice and HCl (dil.) and then filtered. The yellow solid residue was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 120°, yield 0.25 g. (95%). (Found: Cl, 13.41. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.73%).

Method II.—Using the same amounts of the starting materials in absolute ethanol and 10% sodium methoxide solution (0.1 ml), prepared by dissolving metallic sodium (1g.) in pure methanol (10 ml), the same compound was obtained in similar yield. It was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 120°. (Found: Cl, 13.41. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 13.73%).

2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-2-nitrochalkone (Method III).—To 2-hydroxy-3-chloroacetophenone (1 g.), *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 g.), and glycine (1 g.), dissolved in ethanol (16.5 ml), was added the buffer solution (20 ml) and the mixture was left for 2 days. The yellow needles separating were crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 200° (decomp.), yield 0.45 g. (45%). (Found: Cl, 11.52. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4NCl$ requires Cl, 11.69%).

2'-Acetoxy-3'-chlorochalkone.—A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorochalkone (0.5 g.), pyridine (4 drops), and acetic anhydride (3-4 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. The content was then poured on cold water and the solid separating was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 94°, yield 0.21 g. (50%). (Found: Cl, 11.50. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 11.51%).

2'-Methoxy-3'-chlorochalkone.—2'-Hydroxy-3'-chlorochalkone (0.5 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (0.75 ml) and K_2CO_3 (4 g.) on a water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue was washed with hot acetone. On removal of acetone from the filtrate and on addition of water, a colorless solid separated, which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 136°, yield 0.23 g. (65%). (Found: Cl, 12.98. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.02%).

The IR spectral measurements were made with a Perkin-Elmer Model 21 Double Beam Infrared spectrophotometer by taking the sample in a paraffin mull. The IR data of the chalkones are recorded in Table II. A study of these data leads to the following interesting conclusions with regard to carbonyl and ethylenic absorptions.

TABLE II

No.	Chalkone.	Absorption (in μ)	
		C=O.	-C=C-
1	Chalkone	6.0s	6.23s 6.36m
2	2'-Hydroxy-	6.1s	6.35s
3	2-Hydroxy-	6.1s	6.27s 6.33w
4	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-	6.1m	6.2 m
5	2,2'-Dihydroxy-3'-chloro-	6.125s	6.21w
6	2'-Methoxy-3'-chloro-	6.0m	6.22sh 6.26s
7	2'-Acetoxy-3'-chloro-	6.04 s 6.0 s	6.19s 6.25w
8	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-	6.07m	6.31s 6.36sh

TABLE II (contd.)

Sl. No.	Chalkones.	Absorption in μ	
		C=O.	-C=C-
9.	2,2'-Dihydroxy-5'-chloro-	6.1s	6.2m 6.32s
10.	2'-Methoxy-6'-chloro-	5.97s 6.1sh	6.2m 6.25sh
11.	2'-Acetoxy-5'-chloro-	5.67s 5.96s	6.19s 6.22sh
12.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-	6.05s	6.21s
13.	4'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-nitro-	6.02w	6.2w 6.25m
14.	4'-Methoxy-3'-chloro-	5.98s	6.22sh 6.25s
15.	4'-Acetoxy-3'-chloro-	5.64s 6.0s	6.2s 6.325w
16.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-	5.87s	6.1s
17.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-nitro-	6.05s	6.27 6.35sh

N.B. s denotess strong, sh, shoulder, m, medium, and w, weak.

Influence of Structural Changes on Carbonyl Absorption

It is well known that whenever there is an increased opportunity for the contribution of the ionic resonance structure, (A) to the carbonyl group (B), a shift to higher wave length or lower frequency is observed.

Thus in acetone, the band for the unconjugated carbonyl group appears at 5.81μ (1718 cm^{-1}), whereas benzylideneacetophenone shows its carbonyl absorption at 1659 cm^{-1} (6.02μ) due to conjugation with a phenyl group and an aliphatic double bond.

(a). *Hydroxyl Group in 2- or 2'-position.*—Introduction of a hydroxyl group in 2'- or 2-position is expected to shift the carbonyl band to a higher wave length. This expectation has been realised, as is evident from the positions of the carbonyl bands of the chalkones No. 1, 2, and 3 (Table II).

(b). *Effect of Substituents in 5'- or 3'-position (with Hydroxyl Group in 2'- or/and 2-position).*—If a group is placed in *ortho* or *para* position with respect to hydroxyl group and in *meta* position with respect to carbonyl group, invariably an hypsochromic shift is observed to a greater or less extent. The effect of hypsochromic shift depends on the +I and -I effect of the substituent. A substituent with +I effect produces a maximum hypsochromic shift, the amount of which is reduced if the substituent is replaced by other groups having -I effect. Thus while

the carbonyl band of compound No. 2 (2'-hydroxychalkone) and No. 3 (2-hydroxychalkone) (vide Table II), unsubstituted in *ortho* or *para* position with respect to hydroxyl group, appears at 6.1 μ , compound No. 16 (2'-hydroxy-5'-methylchalkone) (Table II) having a methyl group (with +I effect) in *para* position with respect to hydroxyl group and *meta* position with respect to carbonyl group exhibits its carbonyl absorption at 5.875 μ . If the methyl group is, however, replaced by an electron-attracting group, such as NO₂ group (with -I effect) as in compound No. 17 (2'-hydroxy-5'-nitrochalkone) (Table II), the extent of hypsochromic shift is considerably reduced and the carbonyl absorption appears at 6.05 μ . Similarly, if the 5'-position carries a chlorine atom, as in compound No. 8 (2'-hydroxy-5'-chlorochalkone) (Table II), hypsochromic shift is again observed and the carbonyl band appears at 6.07 μ . As the chlorine atom is at the *meta* position with respect to carbonyl group, the resonance interaction of chlorine and the carbonyl group is excluded.

(c). *Hydroxyl Group in both 2'-and 2-positions.*—The carbonyl band of compound No. 5 (Table II) appears at a slightly higher value at 6.125 μ , ascribable to two -OH groups in *o*- and *o'*-positions. The absorption of carbonyl band in the higher region is also observed in the case of compound No. 9 (Table II). This is expected since bathochromic shift caused by two -OH groups in the *o*- and *o'*- positions should be greater than that caused by one *ortho*-hydroxyl group.

(d). *Methylation of 2'-Hydroxyl Group.*—Methylation of 2'-hydroxyl group causes an hypsochromic shift. This will be evident from a comparison of IR data of the chalkones No. 4, 6, 8, and 10 (Table II).

(e). *Acetylation of 2'-Hydroxyl Group.*—When the 2'-hydroxyl group is acetylated, hypsochromic shift is also observed, as is evident from the comparison of the positions of carbonyl absorption of compounds No. 4, 7, 8, and 11 (Table II). This is expected on the basis of similar observations made in the case of *o*-hydroxy- and *o*-acetoxy-acetophenones, carbonyl band appearing at 6.11 μ and 5.96 μ respectively.

(f). *Hydroxyl Group in 4'-position.*—A hydroxyl group in 4'-position, like that in 2'-position, also causes a bathochromic shift, though the extent of this shift is less in the former case. This will be evident from the carbonyl absorption of the chalkones No. 4 and 12 (Table II).

(g). *Methylation and Acetylation of 4'-Hydroxyl Group.*—If the hydroxyl group at 4'-position is methylated or acetylated, hypsochromic shift is observed, similar to that observed in the case of 2-hydroxyl group. This will be evident from the carbonyl absorption of compounds No. 4, 6, 7, 12, 14, and 15 (Table II).

(h) *Nitro Group at 4-position.*—The nitro group at 4-position causes an hypsochromic shift, as expected. This is indicated by the carbonyl absorption of compounds No. 12 and 13 (Table II).

Influence of Structural Changes on -C=C- Absorption

(a). *Effect of Hydroxyl Group in 2- or 2'-position.*—In unsubstituted chalkone the absorption band for -C=C- group appears at 6.23 μ with a weak shoulder at 6.27 μ . When a hydroxyl group is placed at 2'-position, the ethylenic band shows up at 6.35 μ

with a weak shoulder at 6.325 μ . A hydroxy substituent at 2-position also gives rise to an intense peak at 6.33 μ for the $-C=C-$ group. Thus introduction of hydroxyl group at 2- or 2'-position gives rise to a bathochromic shift for the $-C=C-$ absorption. These generalisations have been made from the ethylenic absorption of compounds No. 1, 2, and 3 (Table II).

(a). *Effect of Substituents in 5'-positions.*—As has been observed in the case of carbonyl absorption, substituents with $-I$ effect, placed at 5'-position (with a hydroxyl group at 2'-position), produce the maximum hypsochromic shift. The amount of hypsochromic shift is decreased if the substituent having $+I$ effect is replaced by other groups having $-I$ effect. The ethylenic absorptions of the following compounds clearly illustrate this.

TABLE III

*No.	Chalcones.	Absorption (in μ .)
2	2'-Hydroxy-	6.35a
3	2-Hydroxy-	6.33
16	2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-	6.15
17	2'-Hydroxy-5'-nitro-	6.27
8	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-	6.31.

* The number refers to those in Table II.

(c). *Methylation or Acetylation of 2'-Hydroxyl Group.*—By methylation or acetylation of the 2'-hydroxyl group, hypsochromic shift in the absorption band for the $-C=C-$ is observed. This will be evident by comparing the absorption band of the compounds No. 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, and 11 (Table II).

The authors are grateful to the United States Govt. (India Wheat Loan Fund) for the generous gift of a Model 21 Double Beam Infrared spectrophotometer and to the Board of Scientific & Industrial Research, Orissa, for a research grant to support these investigations.